
The Current Situation and Development Trend of Dust Control Technology in Fully Mechanized Mining Work

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Abstract: With the continuous improvement of coal mining intensity and mechanization level in China, the dust hazard problem in fully mechanized mining faces has become increasingly prominent, seriously threatening miners' occupational health and mine safety production. This paper systematically reviews the current status and development trends of dust control technologies in fully mechanized mining faces, mainly introducing the dust removal mechanisms, system components, key parameters, and engineering applications of mainstream technologies including spray dust removal, foam dust removal, negative pressure dust removal, and air curtain dust control. The advantages and limitations of each technology are analyzed. Furthermore, the research progress of novel technologies such as active magnetized water spray, micron-level dry mist, electrostatic dust removal, and biological dust suppression are summarized. Finally, the development directions of dust control technologies in fully mechanized mining faces are forecasted from the perspectives of intelligent collaborative control, green environmental-friendly dust suppressant research and development, and multi-technology integration, aiming to provide references for efficient coal mine dust control.

Keywords: fully mechanized mining face; dust control; spray dust removal; foam dust removal; negative pressure dust removal; air curtain dust control

1. Introduction

Background and significance of study

As China's basic energy source, coal occupies a pivotal position in China's national economic and social development. According to the National Bureau of Statistics, although the proportion of coal in the primary energy consumption structure is on a downward trend, it is expected to remain at about 50% by 2030, which is the ballast stone of China's energy supply [1]. In recent years, with the continuous expansion of coal mine production and mining scale in China, the concentration of mine dust has also continued to increase, posing a serious threat to mine safety production and the occupational health of miners [2].

According to the statistics of the National Health Commission, as of the end of 2021, a total of 915,000 occupational pneumoconiosis patients have been reported nationwide, of which about 450,000 are still alive, and the annual number of deaths due to pneumoconiosis in the coal industry is higher than the total number of deaths from various production accidents in the same period. Studies have shown that more than 80% of the coal dust in key coal mines in China is explosive, and since the 20th century, there have been 15 extra-large coal dust explosions in China, resulting in nearly 1,000 deaths. Third, the hazard of the working environment, high concentration of dust reduces the visibility of the working space, affects the reliability of equipment and safe production [3].

With the popularization and application of large-scale mining and intelligent mining technology, the dust production and dust distribution characteristics of the fully mechanized mining face are more complex and changeable. According to the on-site investigation, without any dust prevention measures, the weighted total

dust concentration in the main working area of the personnel in the high-mechanized mining face can reach 500~850 mg/m³, and the breathable dust concentration can reach 300~500 mg/m³[4]. Therefore, the study of dust control technology in fully mechanized mining has important theoretical significance and engineering value for ensuring the health of miners and improving the level of safe production.

Research status at home and abroad

Aiming at the difficulty of dust prevention and control in fully mechanized mining faces, scholars and engineers at home and have carried out extensive theoretical research and engineering practice. At present, a traditional dust control system has been formed, with spray dust reduction, foam dust removal, negative pressure dust removal and ventilation dust control as the core. Meanwhile, phased achievements have been made in frontier fields such as new dust suppression materials and intelligent precise dust control, providing support for the iterative upgrading of high-efficiency dust removal technologies in fully mechanized mining [5]. Spray dust reduction is the most widely used basic underground dust prevention technology due to its simple structure, good economy and strong adaptability to working conditions. Relevant studies show that spray pressure is a key parameter determining atomization quality and dust removal efficiency [6]. The active magnetized water spray technology, through the coupling regulation of surfactant modification and water magnetization, effectively improves the wetting and capture ability of water mist to hydrophobic fine coal dust, significantly enhances the comprehensive dust removal effect of the working face, and makes up for the deficiency of traditional pure water spray in controlling respirable dust [7]. Relying on the multi-coupling mechanisms of medium coverage, wetting and adhesion, foam dust removal has the advantage of efficient capture of multi-size dust, and its comprehensive dust removal performance is 3~5 times that of traditional spraying. Among them, the ZPJ series mine foam dust removal device can achieve a foaming ratio of more than 20 times, and the total dust removal efficiency of the working face exceeds 85%, showing good engineering applicability [8]. Negative pressure dust removal constructs a negative pressure flow field through Venturi effect or fan suction, and forms a gas-liquid coupled purification system combined with spray mist field, which can actively collect and purify suspended dust-laden airflow. The airborne negative pressure dust removal device for shearers and the integrated negative pressure-micro fog dust removal equipment for high-cutting-height working faces can achieve total dust control efficiency of more than 66.5% and 80% respectively, effectively adapting to complex and high-dust production conditions [9-10]. As an active airflow blocking technology, air curtain dust control can realize zonal dust isolation by constructing a directional airflow barrier. The airborne integrated air curtain system can form a stable dust-proof barrier in the shearer operating area, with a dust reduction efficiency of 90.47% in the operating area, showing outstanding precise dust control effect [11]. On the basis of continuous optimization of traditional technologies, new green and refined dust removal technologies such as micron-level dry fog dust suppression, electrostatic precipitation, acoustic agglomeration and bio-based dust suppression have been gradually applied, effectively making up for the shortcomings of traditional technologies such as limited control effect on fine respirable dust and insufficient environmental protection. Among them, the biological dust suppression material prepared based on *Bacillus subtilis* has green advantages such as excellent wetting and consolidation performance, natural degradability and no secondary pollution [12]. Meanwhile, studies on the optimization of air curtain parameters have also provided important theoretical support for the precise and large-scale application of airflow dust control technology [13].

2. Traditional Dust Control Technology

Spray dust removal technology

pray dust reduction serves as the most widely adopted physical dust purification technology for fully mechanized mining faces, trapping suspended coal dust via atomized water mist based on four coupled mechanisms: inertial collision, interfacial interception, Brownian diffusion and particle coagulation. Dust removal performance is primarily governed by the particle size matching degree between droplets and dust, and the optimal droplet-to-dust size ratio is confirmed as 1:1 to 5:1 [14]. Fine atomization with droplet sizes of 1~50 μm is required for effective control of hazardous respirable dust below 10 μm. The complete spray dust reduction system adopts a modular configuration composed of water supply, filtration, high-pressure pressurization, pipeline and atomizing nozzle units [15]. The water supply and filtration modules guarantee clean water delivery to avoid pipeline deposition and nozzle blockage, while the pressurization unit provides

5~10 MPa water pressure to support refined atomization. As the core component, built-in nozzles realize precise source dust suppression near cutting teeth, and external nozzles arranged around the shearer drum form a closed mist curtain to prevent dust diffusion.

To overcome the insufficient capacity of traditional pure water spraying in controlling hydrophobic fine coal dust, active magnetized water spray technology has been developed and widely applied in engineering scenarios. This innovative technology optimizes the surface physicochemical characteristics of spray medium through the coupling effect of surfactant modification and water magnetization, effectively enhancing the wetting, penetration and agglomeration performance for fine coal dust. Its optimal operating parameters include a surfactant mass fraction of 0.03%, magnetic field strength of 300~350 mT, water flow velocity of 4 m/s and magnetization distance of 8 m. Relevant tests show that the optimized medium reduces dust settling time by 44.26% to 34.5 s. Field practice in the 24130 intelligent fully mechanized mining face of Pingmei No.10 Coal Mine achieves 85.3% respirable dust reduction efficiency and 90.8% total dust reduction efficiency, fully demonstrating the prominent technical superiority and reliable engineering applicability of this technology in fine dust governance.

Foam dust removal technology

Foam dust removal is a physicochemical coupled dust purification technology that utilizes gas-liquid two-phase foam media to capture and settle coal dust in fully mechanized mining faces, with three core synergistic dust removal mechanisms [16]. The spatial coverage and barrier effect enables stable foam to fully cover the shearer cutting drum, confining coal breaking and dust generation within the foam layer to suppress dust diffusion at the source. The wetting modification effect is achieved by surfactant components in foam liquid film, which reduce water surface tension, enhance the wetting and penetration ability for hydrophobic coal dust, and promote the agglomeration and settlement of fine particles. Relying on moderate viscosity characteristics, the foam medium can physically adsorb and restrain suspended dust of various particle sizes, reduce fine dust escape, and improve the overall capture efficiency of multi-scale dust.

Compared with traditional spray dust reduction, foam dust removal presents prominent technical advantages in dust capture performance, fine dust adaptability and water conservation [17]. With identical water consumption, foam media possesses a larger specific surface area than water droplets, increasing solid-liquid contact probability and overall dust purification efficiency. The inherent viscosity of foam enables synchronous capture of coarse and respirable fine dust, compensating for the poor fine dust control capability of conventional water mist. The added active ingredients further optimize solution wettability to adapt to the purification of hydrophobic coal dust. Moreover, foam dust removal consumes only 30%~80% of the water used in traditional spraying, which meets the technical requirements of high-efficiency dust prevention and the green development concept of modern coal mining.

Negative pressure dust removal technology

Negative pressure dust removal is an active dust control technology based on fluid dynamic ejection mechanism, which constructs a steady negative pressure flow field via Venturi effect or fan aerodynamic power to actively collect dispersed dust-laden airflow and form a gas-liquid coupled purification system with fine spray mist [18]. For Venturi-type dust removal, high-pressure water flowing through the converging channel increases flow velocity and reduces local pressure, forming a stable negative pressure zone to entrain dust-laden airflow into the atomization area. The induced dust particles collide, coagulate and agglomerate with droplets to achieve solid-gas separation and dust sedimentation. In fan-driven negative pressure systems, the high-speed rotating impeller produces a centrifugal pressure difference to shear water and dust airflow, forming a uniform fine mist field. Enhanced gas-solid mixing promotes sufficient bonding and agglomeration of fine dust and mist particles, which eventually form coal slime deposits and realize refined airflow purification.

Based on differences in power generation mechanisms, structural configurations and working condition adaptability, underground negative pressure dust removal systems are classified into negative pressure entrainment type, hydrodynamic type and circulating negative pressure type [19], with distinct operational characteristics and application scenarios. The Venturi-based negative pressure entrainment dust collector requires no auxiliary fan, featuring high integration and simple maintenance, and is applicable to intermittent dust pollution during hydraulic support movement. The hydrodynamic dust collector relies on the coordination of high-pressure spray and negative pressure suction, presenting rapid atomization response and strong dust

removal linkage, which adapts to continuous high-intensity dust generation during coal cutting. The circulating negative pressure dust collector realizes iterative purification of dust-laden airflow and is primarily applied for steady global dust control in the return air roadway of fully mechanized mining faces.

Air curtain dust control technology

Air curtain dust control is an active airflow barrier technology for precise dust prevention, which reconstructs local roadway flow fields through directional jet regulation [20]. By installing air curtain generators on roadway sidewalls or shearer bodies, continuous high-pressure and high-speed directional airflow is produced to form a stable, closed axial air curtain barrier. This technique establishes an airflow isolation layer between dust diffusion zones and personnel working areas, spatially blocking the migration and penetration of high-concentration dust generated during coal cutting and support shifting, and achieving effective zoned dust isolation. Supported by planar jet dynamics, dust two-phase motion theory and flow field pressure balance principle, the directional jet constructs a stable pressure gradient on both sides of the air curtain. The formed pressure difference counteracts dust penetration motivation induced by airflow turbulence, suppresses disordered dust diffusion, and realizes efficient blocking of both fine and coarse suspended dust with the advantages of active control and zero medium consumption.

The dust barrier performance and operational stability of air curtain systems are dominated by the coupling effects of jet wind speed, air outlet layout, air supply volume and air curtain thickness [21]. Parameter matching is essential for maintaining continuous and intact air curtain structure and reliable dust control performance. The optimal jet wind speed ranges from 20 to 30 m/s; insufficient wind speed causes curtain discontinuity and dust penetration, while excessive speed disturbs original roadway airflow and induces secondary dust raising. An air outlet layout approximately 30 m away from the working face effectively avoids near-field airflow interference and ensures complete and stable air curtain formation. A rated air supply volume of 400 m³/min guarantees sufficient jet entrainment and full-section coverage without dust control blind areas. Moreover, a rational air curtain thickness of 1.4–2.5 m well adapts to roadway flow characteristics and on-site dust diffusion rules, significantly restrains lateral dust penetration, and optimizes zoned dust blocking accuracy under complex fully mechanized mining conditions.

3. New Dust Control Technology

Micron-level dry mist dust suppression technology

Micron-level dry fog dust suppression technology is a refined dust removal technology developed to address the challenge of controlling respirable fine dust in fully mechanized mining faces. Relying on the high particle-size matching between 1–10 μm ultra-fine droplets and fine dust, it promotes the agglomeration of suspended fine dust into large composite particles through coupled mechanisms including inertial collision, interfacial interception, Brownian diffusion, and particle coagulation, ultimately achieving rapid settlement and purification under gravity [22]. Compared with traditional spray dust removal technology, this technology offers significant performance and operational advantages. Ultra-fine droplets can remain suspended in the underground airflow field for an extended period, with an effective action duration exceeding 90 s, greatly prolonging the dust capture cycle. Comprehensive dust suppression efficiency for fine dust can reach above 90%, precisely overcoming the bottleneck in respirable dust control. It exhibits excellent water-saving performance with a water reduction rate of 70%–90%, substantially reducing water consumption for underground dust removal. Meanwhile, the moisture increment of coal materials during operation is less than 0.02%, which does not alter the physicochemical properties or quality of coal, adapting to the requirements of continuous and large-scale coal mining.

Electrostatic dust removal technology

Electrostatic precipitation technology is a high-efficiency modified dust removal technology optimized based on the principle of charge adsorption. By utilizing the charging characteristics of dust particles and atomized droplets, it strengthens the adsorption and coupling effect of gas–solid two-phase flow via Coulomb attraction, significantly improving fine dust capture efficiency [23]. Underground coal dust particles generally carry positive charges through triboelectrification during crushing, collision, and diffusion. A negative high-voltage electrostatic generator can uniformly charge atomized droplets with negative electricity. The Coulomb force between opposite charges effectively enhances the adsorption, wrapping, and agglomeration capacity of water

mist toward hydrophobic fine coal dust, overcoming the technical defects of traditional water mist such as weak adsorption force and high escape rate for fine dust. Existing experimental studies confirm that the electrostatic coupled dust removal mode can further increase dust removal efficiency by 20%–30% on the basis of traditional spraying, representing an important technical direction for high-efficiency fine dust control.

Sonic condensation technology

Acoustic agglomeration technology is a passive fine dust purification technology based on acoustic field dynamics, which drives active physical agglomeration of roadway aerosol particles by constructing a high-intensity steady-state acoustic field [24]. Excited by a strong acoustic field of specific frequency, suspended fine dust particles in the working face undergo intense high-frequency vibration driven by acoustic energy and obtain high-intensity kinetic energy. Relying on Brownian diffusion, hydrodynamic coupling, and acoustic resonance effects, the collision contact probability and agglomeration efficiency between fine dust particles are greatly improved. Submicron and micron fine particles that are difficult to settle agglomerate with each other to form dense large-size particle clusters, weakening the suspension and diffusion characteristics of fine dust and thus achieving high-efficiency settlement and dust removal. This technology can effectively compensate for the insufficient capacity of traditional dust removal technologies in controlling ultra-fine dust.

Bio-based dust suppressant technology

Bio-based dust suppression technology is a green and environmentally friendly dust suppression technology using natural degradable biomass materials as the base matrix. It has become a research hotspot in green coal mine dust prevention due to its advantages of degradability, no secondary pollution, and good operational adaptability [25]. Current mainstream materials include starch-based, cellulose-based, lignin-based, and microbial-based types, which exhibit better environmental compatibility and application sustainability than traditional chemical dust suppressants. Relevant studies show that new bio-dust suppressants prepared via microbial fermentation possess excellent wetting modification properties. The BDS bio-dust suppression solution developed by Wang Hetang et al. achieves a contact angle of only 11.19° with coal dust at a mass concentration of 6 mg/L, and the wetting performance toward hydrophobic coal dust is improved by more than 63.5% compared with traditional chemical dust suppressants, effectively realizing wetting agglomeration and consolidation settlement of fine coal dust. On this basis, microbial-induced calcium carbonate precipitation (MICP), as an advanced green dust suppression technology, achieves in-situ solidification and prevention of dust through microbial biochemical reactions [26]. Its core mechanism is that functional microorganisms secrete urease to catalyze urea hydrolysis and produce carbonate ions, which combine with environmental calcium ions to form calcium carbonate precipitates, filling the pores of coal dust particles and forming a dense and stable consolidated layer to inhibit dust lifting and diffusion from the source. The microbial dust suppression system developed by Li Zhigang et al. can form a complete dust-proof consolidated layer in coal storage and transportation scenarios, with a material biodegradation rate exceeding 82%. It combines stable dust control performance and green environmental characteristics, showing promising engineering application prospects.

4. Conclusions and Prospects

Main conclusions

- (1) Traditional spray dust reduction technology remains the fundamental dust control method for fully mechanized mining faces. Dust removal efficiency can be effectively improved through parameter optimization, such as increasing spray pressure and improving nozzle structure. Modified technologies including active magnetized water spray and atomized sealing have demonstrated promising application prospects in fully mechanized mining faces, with the dust removal efficiency for respirable dust exceeding 85%.
- (2) Foam dust removal technology utilizes the triple effects of foam coverage, wetting, and adhesion. Its capture efficiency for respirable dust is 3~5 times higher than that of traditional spraying, while reducing water consumption by 30%~80%, presenting remarkable economic and environmental benefits.
- (3) Negative pressure dust removal technology entrains dust-laden air via the Venturi effect and achieves high-efficiency purification combined with spray atomization. The total dust removal efficiency can reach more than 80%~90%.

- (4) Air curtain dust control technology forms an airflow isolation barrier in the driver's working area, showing a significant blocking effect on respirable dust. It can reduce the dust concentration in the driver's area from above 2000 mg/m³ to below 300 mg/m³.
- (5) Various new technologies have emerged continuously, such as micron-level dry fog, electrostatic precipitation, acoustic agglomeration, and bio-based dust suppressants. Multi-technology collaborative control represents an important development direction in the future.

Development trends and prospects

Based on the current research status and development requirements, dust control technologies for fully mechanized mining faces will present the following development trends:

Intelligent control: Combined with real-time dust concentration monitoring and automatic adjustment technologies, adaptive optimization of spray parameters can be realized. The application of Internet of Things, big data and artificial intelligence technologies will promote the development of dust control systems toward intellectualization and unmanned operation.

Multi-technology integration: Synergistic control of multiple technologies such as spray, foam, negative pressure and air curtain will form a multi-source, zonal and hierarchical control system to maximize the comprehensive dust removal efficiency.

Green environmental protection: The research and application of bio-based dust suppressants and microbial dust reduction technologies can achieve the environmental goals of zero pollution and zero emission, and boost the green development of the coal industry.

Precise control: High-efficiency capture technologies for respirable dust (less than 10 μm) will become the research focus, and charged spray, ultra-fine atomization and other technologies have broad application prospects.

System integration: Dust control systems will be deeply integrated with intelligent working faces, and virtual simulation optimization and real-time control will be realized based on digital twin technology.

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Data Availability Statement

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article and its supplementary information files.

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